

MANAGEMENT OF CONFLICT AND CHANGE TOWARD HAPPINESS AT WORK AND SOCIAL TRUST OF TEACHERS

AUDREY DENISE C. LIMBO¹

DELON A. CHING²

audreydenise.limbo@deped.gov.ph¹

delon.ching@lspu.edu.ph²

0000-0003-0017-3668¹

0000-0003-1435-4371²

Sta. Catalina Central School, Candelaria, Quezon, Philippines¹

Laguna State Polytechnic University, San Pablo City, Laguna, Philippines²

ABSTRACT

In recent years, there has been the evolution of interest and significant growth in the study of conflict and change management in the emergence of new forms of school workplace organization. Candelaria East District school heads were reshuffled. School heads who rendered 5 years and more in their school assignments are prioritized in the transfer. Restructuring of school heads in Candelaria East District brought about changes and conflict within the organization. The researcher aims to determine the management of conflict and change toward happiness at work and social trust. This study utilized a descriptive and correlational type of research wherein it used a survey questionnaire through the help of google form for the safest distribution and collection of data in this time of the pandemic. The respondents of the study were 130 elementary teachers who are currently employed in eight schools in the District of Candelaria East, Division of Quezon that conducted last March 2021. The result showed that the school heads manifested the proper management of conflict and change to their organization. The extent of happiness at work of the teachers was particularly at the level of very happy while the social trust in the workplace has great extent. Based on the findings, school heads managed conflict and change which leads to happiness and social trust of teachers in their workplace. Furthermore, it was also revealed that the sub- variable of management of change, coercive style significantly predicts both happiness and social trust of teachers. The researcher recommends that school heads must understand that happiness at work and social trust is achieved when the school heads manifested the right approach in management. The happier at work and socially trusted the teachers is to better health and well-being, more creative and effective problem solver, more productive and innovative in the workplace.

Keywords: Management of Conflict, Management of Change, Happiness at Work, Social Trust